

DISPERSIV MUHITLARDA QUVURLARDAGI LAMINAR HARAKATNING DEVOR YONIDA SILJISH EFFEKTI

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Bugungi kunda plastik muhitlar bilan ishlash keng ommalashib bormaqda va dispers sistemalarning sathidagi harakatlarni o'rganish ham tkmillashmoqa. Shu boisdan dispers sistemalarining sathidagi anominal harakati uning devor yonida siljishdan iboratdir. Devor qatlamidagi muhit devor yonida siljish tezligini oshiradi va bu tezlik quvur diametriga bog'liq. Dispers muhitning harakat jarayonida devor qatlamini siljishini hisobga olgan holda bosim o'zgarishi va sarfi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik quyidagicha:

$$\frac{Q}{\pi R^3 \tau_w} = \frac{\xi(\tau_w)}{R} + \varphi(\tau_w) \quad (1)$$

bunda

$$\xi(\tau_w) = \frac{S(\tau_w)}{\tau_w}, \tau_w = \frac{\Delta P}{2l} R. \quad (2)$$

Qovushqoq plastik suyuqlikning silindir shaklidagi quvurda harakati uchun quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\varphi(\tau_w) = \frac{1}{4\mu} \left[1 - \frac{4}{3} \frac{\tau_0}{\tau_w} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_w} \right)^4 \right] \quad (3)$$

Qovushqoq plastik muhitning devor osti muhitini hisobga olganda tekis quvurdagi harakatini qaraymiz. Tekis turba uchun qovushqoq plastik suyuqlikning harakat modeli quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$\tau = \tau_0 - \mu \frac{du}{dx}. \quad (4)$$

Bu ifodani integrallab quyidagini hosil qilamiz

$$u = -\frac{1}{\mu} \int \tau dx + \frac{\tau_0}{\mu} x + C \quad (5)$$

bunda u - tezlik, μ - qovushqoqlik koeffitsiyenti, τ_0 - chegaraviy kuchlanish, C-o'zgarimasni aniqlash uchun quyidagi shartdan foydalanamiz

$$u = S(\tau_w) \quad \text{yoki} \quad x = h \quad (6)$$

(6) formulani hisobga olgan holda va tekis quvur uchun hosil qilamiz:

$$\tau = \frac{\Delta P}{l} x$$

va quyidagini formulani

$$u = \frac{\Delta P}{2\mu l} (h^2 - x^2) - \frac{\tau_0}{\mu} (h - x) + S(\tau_\omega) \quad (7)$$

bu yerda $S(\tau_\omega)$ - devorda siljish tezligi. Suyuqlik sarfi quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadi:

$$\frac{Q}{2h^2\tau_\omega} = \frac{\varepsilon(\tau_\omega)}{h} + \varphi(\tau_\omega) \quad (8)$$

bunda

$$\varphi(\tau_\omega) = \frac{1}{3\mu} \left[1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{\tau_0}{\tau_\omega} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_\omega} \right)^3 \right], \quad \tau_\omega = \frac{\Delta P}{l} h;$$

$\varepsilon(\tau_\omega)$ -samarali sirpanish koeffitsiyenti

Muhit siljiganda devor qatlamidagi suyuqlik qatlamini quyidagicha aniqlaymiz

$$0 \leq \delta \leq y$$

Devor qatlamidagi suyuqlikni Nyuton qonuniga bo'ysunadi deb qaraymiz u holda quyidagi formula hosil bo'ladi.

$$\tau = \frac{R - y}{2} \times \frac{\Delta P}{l} \quad (9)$$

Siljish tezligi quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadi:

$$S(\tau_\omega) = \int_0^\delta \frac{R - y}{2\mu} \frac{\Delta P}{l} dy \quad (10)$$

(10) formulani integrallab va (2) ni hisobga olgan holda quyidagi formulani aniqlaymiz.

$$\delta = R - \sqrt{R^2 - 2\mu R \varepsilon(\tau_\omega)} \quad (11)$$

Demak, tekis quvur uchun

$$\delta = h - \sqrt{R^2 - 2\mu h \varepsilon(\tau_\omega)} \quad (12)$$

formular (11) va (12) dan devor yonidagi suyuqlikning qalinligi δ ni aniqlash mumkin.

Buning uchun $\varepsilon(\tau_\omega)$ ni qiymatlari aniqlangan bo'lishi kerak.

1-rasm.

1-rasmda $\frac{Q}{\pi R^3 \tau_\omega}$ ning $\frac{1}{R}$ ga nisbatan grafigi keltirilgan. Buning uchun $\varepsilon(\tau_\omega)$ da segmenti $\varphi(\tau_\omega)$ bilan qattiq. (11) chi formuladagi $\varepsilon(\tau_\omega)$ bo'yicha $\tau_\omega=0,4$ (1); $\tau_\omega=0,6$ (2); $\tau_\omega=0,8$ (3); $\tau_\omega=1,0$ (4) va $\tau_\omega=1,2$ (5) lar uchun keltirilgan.

(1)-formulaga asosan $\frac{Q}{\pi R^3 \tau_\omega}$ ning $\frac{1}{R}$ ga nisbatan og'ma to'g'ri chiziqlar hosil bo'ladi.

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